

Acetoacetanilide Complexes of Naphthoxides of Titanium(IV)

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Monochloro-, dichloro- and trichloro-titanium(IV) naphthoxides when refluxed with acetoacetanilide (acanH) in appropriate molar ratios in benzene form compounds of composition, $Ti(OC_{10}H_7)_2 \cdot 2acan$, $TiCl(OC_{10}H_7)_2 \cdot 2acan$, $Ti(OC_{10}H_7)_3 \cdot acan$, $TiCl(OC_{10}H_7)_3 \cdot acan$, and $TiCl_2(OC_{10}H_7)_3 \cdot acan$. Based upon elemental analyses, conductance, cryoscopic and infrared spectral studies, their structures have been proposed.

ACETOACETANILIDE (acanH) and its derivatives are well known to form stable chelates with metal chlorides^{1,2}. Chloroalkoxides of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) also form chelates with acetoacetanilide by elimination reaction³ but no corresponding attempt has been made on the isolation of metal phenoxide complexes with such ligands, possibly because metal phenoxides have poor acceptor properties compared to metal halides due to their polymeric character^{4,5}. Nevertheless, under suitable conditions, the intermolecular bridge can be ruptured by the addition of another ligand. Recently, we have isolated addition compounds of naphthoxides of titanium(IV) with tertiary bases⁶ and presently, we report the isolation and characterisation of chelates of naphthoxides of titanium(IV) with acetoacetanilide.

Experimental

Titanium(IV) naphthoxides of composition $TiCl(OC_{10}H_7)_3$, $TiCl_2(OC_{10}H_7)_2$ and $TiCl_3(OC_{10}H_7)$ were prepared by the methods reported earlier⁷. Acetoacetanilide (B.D.H.) was recrystallised from aqueous methanol and the sample having melting point 85° was used for the reactions.

Monochloro-, dichloro- and trichloro-titanium(IV) naphthoxides were taken as suspension in benzene/ carbon tetrachloride and the benzene solution of acetoacetanilide was added in predetermined molar ratios. The contents were then refluxed on a water bath till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. The complexes were isolated either by cooling the resulting solutions or by the addition of petroleum ether to their solutions. The solid compounds so obtained were filtered, washed repeatedly with petroleum ether and finally dried under vacuum.

Titanium was estimated as titanium dioxide, carbon and hydrogen by microanalytical methods and chlorine by Volhard's method. Molecular weights of the adducts were determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene using Beckmann's method.

Infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 infrared spectrophotometers.

Results and Discussion

Acetoacetanilide does not react with monochloro-, dichloro- and trichloro-titanium(IV) naphthoxides at room temperature. However, when the components were refluxed in an inert solvent, evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was observed accompanied by a change in the colour of the solution. Possible elimination reaction may be represented as,

Similar reactions may be written with other naphthoxides of titanium(IV). Stoichiometric composition of the resulting compounds has been established by elemental analysis (Table I). All these compounds are fine crystalline solids having definite melting point. They are moisture-sensitive but are stable in dry atmosphere. They are fairly soluble in benzene, nitrobenzene and acetonitrile. Molar conductance of these compounds in nitrobenzene are typical of the values for non-electrolytes in this solvent as these values are much lower than the values expected for 1 : 1 electrolytes⁸. Molecular weight determinations of the compounds of composition $Ti(OC_{10}H_7)_2 \cdot 2acan$ and $TiCl(OC_{10}H_7) \cdot 2acan$ cryoscopically in nitrobenzene show them to be monomers while the compounds $Ti(OC_{10}H_7)_3 \cdot acan$, $TiCl(OC_{10}H_7)_2 \cdot acan$, and $TiCl_2(OC_{10}H_7) \cdot acan$ are found to be dimers. In the former case, apparently there is a breakdown of the dimeric structure of the parent naphthoxides^{6,7} on complex formation with ligands while the dimeric structure of the parent naphthoxides is retained in the latter case. This observation is supported by ir spectra of these compounds.

Infrared spectrum of the pure ligand shows strong absorption band at 3268 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 3145 cm^{-1} due to intramolecularly bonded N-H group⁹, and the strong band appearing at

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF ACETOACETANILIDE COMPLEXES OF NAPHTHOXIDES OF TITANIUM(IV)

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found(Calcd.)				Molar conductance in nitrobenzene $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Molecular weight in nitrobenzene	
			Ti	Cl	C	H		Found	Calcd.
$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$	Light brown	119	7.21 (7.35)	—	73.17 (73.50)	4.02 (4.74)	1.7	1269	653
$\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$	Light brown	153d	8.72 (8.79)	6.39 (6.50)	65.07 (65.99)	3.80 (4.39)	2.3	—	545.5
$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$	Brown	196	6.91 (6.99)	—	69.16 (69.97)	4.18 (4.95)	3.4	661	686
$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$	Light brown	209	10.83 (10.96)	16.07 (16.21)	53.97 (54.79)	3.87 (3.89)	2.9	831	488
$\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$	Dark brown	158	8.21 (8.29)	6.03 (6.14)	61.76 (62.22)	3.96 (4.66)	2.6	—	578.5

d = decompose.

1727 cm^{-1} due to non-conjugated C=O group. The appearance of this carbonyl band and the absence of any OH stretching vibrations indicate that the ligand under ordinary condition exists almost entirely in the keto form which is also substantiated from the nmr spectrum of the acetoacetanilide where the signals due to OH and CH groups are so small that they can be practically ignored⁹.

It is observed that on complex formation with the naphthoxides of titanium(IV), the carbonyl stretching mode of the ligand shifts to the lower spectral regions at 1578, 1570, 1580, 1572 and 1574 cm^{-1} while the broad N-H stretching mode experiences upward shift to 3292, 3284, 3290, 3314 and 3310 cm^{-1} in the compounds of composition $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$, $\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$, $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$, $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$ and $\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$, respectively. These shifts indicate the absence of nitrogen coordination and is in agreement with the earlier reports on the metal chelates of acetoacetanilide⁹. In the metal chelates of acetylacetonates, Lecomte¹⁰ assigned the uppermost band found in the region 1500-1600 cm^{-1} to a perturbed (or chelated) carbonyl stretching mode and the lower band to the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ stretching mode. However, in the case of present chelate compounds, the first strongest band observed in the region 1500-1600 cm^{-1} and located around 1574 cm^{-1} is assigned predominantly to a carbonyl stretching frequency which is in agreement with the earlier observations^{11,12}.

A strong band observed around 1600 cm^{-1} in the pure ligand and its chelates, assigned primarily to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and to the aromatic ring vibrations remain almost unaltered in the chelates with titanium naphthoxides. Another important band observed at 1661 cm^{-1} assigned to amide-I and band at 1538 cm^{-1} assigned to amide-II of the ligand shifts to the lower and higher frequency regions, respectively on chelation. Possibly these bands are a mixture of N-H bending and C-N stretching modes¹³. The amide-III band (CN stretching and NH bending) and CH_2-C stretching vibrations at 1316 and 1279 cm^{-1} , respectively are shifted slightly to the higher and lower spectral region.

Apart from these bands, the other important bands in the case of the compounds of composition $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$ and $\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$ observed at 602 and 595 cm^{-1} , respectively may be assigned to terminal $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{O}}$ stretching modes^{14,15}. No band that could be assigned to the bridging

$\text{Ti}/\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Ti}$ modes has been observed in these complexes, which suggests that dimeric structure of the parent naphthoxide^{6,7} is ruptured on chelate formation. However, in the compounds of composition $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$ and $\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$ bands due to both terminal $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{O}}$ as well as bridging

$\text{Ti}/\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Ti}$ modes have been observed indicating that bridging is retained even on complexation with the ligands. In addition to these bands, sharp and intense bands at 344, 346 and 340 cm^{-1} in the compounds of composition $\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$, $\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$ and $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$, respectively may be assigned to the terminal $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{Cl}}$ stretching modes. Since the bands observed are simple one and there is no splitting of these bands, a *trans* disposition of chlorines in the compound $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$ is inferred as spectra of compounds with *cis* configuration would have been very complex. Thus based on elemental analyses, conductance, cryoscopic and infrared spectral studies, the compounds of composition $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$, $\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$ and $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$ have been assigned dimeric structure bridging through naphthoxy groups, e.g. $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{acan}$ has the following structure.

However, for the compounds of composition $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$ and $\text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{acan}$, the

following, octahedral type of *trans* structure may be proposed.

Above structure finds support from the structures proposed earlier for various chelates of acetoacetanilide with transition metal¹⁶.

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